

AN UNDERGROUND CISTERN AS THERMAL STORAGE FOR A SUPERMARKET WITHIN THE IWER BUILDING IN PAMPLONA.

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ABSTRACT

In the global process of fighting against climate change there is a need for refurbishment of an aging building park, specially for the case of Spain, with a building stock particularly old. A building usage of interest within the tertiary sector, which accounts for 40% of the energy consumption of buildings, is supermarkets. This is part of the so-called "diffuse sector", due to its variety of thermal consumptions and high ratio of energy consumption per square meter. It is therefore a sector with varied opportunities for energy savings through technologically innovative techniques when refurbishing a building, such as thermal storage. The advantages of this technique have been widely assessed for the residential sector and even in other uses of the tertiary sector, but rarely studied in supermarkets. This is mostly owed to the difficulties in its dynamic thermal modeling, approach that is actually essential for the application of control strategies in complex HVACR and refrigeration systems, like those of supermarkets. Indeed, the refrigeration in a supermarket typically constitutes between 35-50% of its energy consumption and interacts with indoor conditions by the heat transfer from refrigerators and freezers, causing the thermal analysis of a supermarket to follow different standards than other uses in the commercial sector. This specific behavior characterized by the interaction between all its elements requests transient hourly simulations, whose complexity can be enlarged with the presence of thermal storage.

In the present work, the use of a subterranean cistern with potential as thermal storage will be explored in the context of a future supermarket located right on top of it. This is a real case study of a tertiary building located in Pamplona, the IWER building, which will be refurbished in the upcoming months. The annual hourly energy performance of a supermarket with HVACR using heat pumps, a CO₂ refrigeration system and rooftop photovoltaics has been modeled using Design Builder and Energy Plus. Cases with and without thermal storage of both heat and cold were assessed and different control strategies based on PV production and electricity prices were applied. This thermal storage was studied as exploitable for both the HVACR system and the refrigeration system of the supermarket, thus exploring new possibilities for the application of thermal storage in the supermarket sector.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context and state of the art

The battle against climate change extends into the realm of building refurbishment, particularly as building stock ages, exemplified by Spain's outdated building stock (*Residencial, Comercial e Institucional*, n.d.). Forty percent of all energy consumed by buildings is attributed to the tertiary sector. (Annunziata et al., 2013; *In Focus: Energy Efficiency in Buildings* / *Comisión Europea*, n.d.). Within this sector, there are subsets with distinct energy usage profiles, among which are supermarkets, categorized within the "diffuse sector." Supermarkets exhibit diverse thermal consumption patterns and have a notably higher energy consumption per square meter compared to other segments of the tertiary sector (Cecchinato et al., 2012; Ríos Fernández & Roqueñí, 2018).

This opens up the possibility of applying novel technologies adapted to the unique energy profile of supermarkets, with Thermal Energy Storage (TES) being an interesting candidate. TES has demonstrated its advantages and applications both in the residential sector and in some cases in the tertiary sector, achieving energy and economic savings through peak shaving and production control strategies. (*Executive Summary – Electricity Market Report – Update 2023 – Analysis - IEA*, n.d.; Li, Rosengarten, et al., 2022; Ragoowansi et al., 2023). Other studies have exploited TES and ITES (Ice Thermal Energy Storage) applications for supermarkets with favorable results, albeit requiring complex ad hoc models simulated in advanced tools like TRNSYS for each case. (Toffoletti et al., 2024).

These studies underscore the unique characteristic of supermarkets energy consumption: a substantial energy consumption in refrigeration (Mylona, Kolokotroni, Tsamos, et al., 2017). Refrigeration in a supermarket constitutes approximately 50% of the total electricity consumption (Ríos Fernández & Roqueñí, 2018) and must therefore be accounted for in any energetic assessment. Additionally, refrigeration imposes an additional load on the HVACR in heating mode and alleviates load in cooling mode. As such, energy simulations must accurately model this interaction between systems (Leerbeck et al., 2023; Mylona, Kolokotroni, Tsamos, et al., 2017).

On the other hand, TES applications require at least hourly precision analysis (Lyu et al., 2022; Osterman & Stritih, 2021) since its advantages come from intraday peak shaving as well as taking advantage of the most beneficial hours to accumulate energy, such as PV production hours or hours when grid prices are lowest (Chadly et al., 2023).

This study aims to explore the potential utilization of an underground cistern as a TES system for a supermarket situated above it within the IWER building in Pamplona, serving as a real case study, in the context of the oPEN Lab project. A workflow based on Design Builder and Energy Plus is proposed to model the annual hourly energy use of the supermarket, incorporating HVACR systems utilizing heat pumps, a CO₂ transcritical refrigeration system, and rooftop photovoltaics. Energy Plus transcritical CO₂ refrigeration model is seldom referenced in the literature. Described only as simplistic and in some rare cases applied with no validation study for the transcritical module (Li, Sun, et al., 2022; Stovall & Baxter, 2010) the authors relied on empirical and literature-driven data (Mitsopoulos et al., 2019) from a real supermarket study for validation purposes.

As for the TES, the scope of the project regards studying TES applications for HVAC (both heat and cold storage) as well as TES coupled with the refrigeration cycle. This paper encompasses the first steps into this simulations the modelling of the refrigeration cycle and a first approach at HVAC hot and cold TES are assessed. The first steps in the optimization process of controlling the TES, an overcharge strategy (Heinz & Rieberer, 2021) for photovoltaic exploitation, is also conducted and presented to give context to the importance of an appropriate refrigeration cycle modelling.

The objectives of this paper are:

- Developing and validating a transcritical CO₂ refrigeration cycle model using Energy Plus and validating its operation for supermarket applications.
- Showing the first steps in simulating and analyzing the results of a supermarket in Pamplona with a TES system for HVAC uses. The thermal and HVACR model was done in Design Builder and the addition of the validated refrigeration in Energy Plus.

In order to accomplish the attempted objectives, the work was divided into two steps. First, the Energy Plus engineering guide and input-output reference were utilized to model a transcritical CO₂ refrigeration system using manufacturer data and the Energy Plus database. This model underwent validation against the findings of an empirical and literature-based study (Mitsopoulos et al., 2019) conducted on a supermarket in Athens, Greece.

Subsequently, the model was applied to an specific case study: a prospective supermarket located within the IWER building in Pamplona, with an underground cistern serving as a TES. Simulations were conducted both with and without integrating the refrigeration system to evaluate its impact, as well as subsequent simulations following the addition of TES to the HVACR system to observe the initial outcomes of its implementation. This preliminary TES simulation results are presented to show the influence of including and adequately modelling refrigeration. Delving deeply into the HVAC system definition, TES optimization and possible TES applications in the refrigeration system in the presented software is left for future works in this project.

2 TRANSCRITICAL CO₂ REFRIGERATION IN ENERGY PLUS MODELLING AND VALIDATION

The transcritical CO₂ system was selected as the refrigeration system due to its growing popularity as a low-GWP refrigerant option, free from toxicity or flammability concerns (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2017).

The original working software for this project, Design Builder, lacks specific modules for simulating refrigeration systems. Meanwhile, the EnergyPlus software, which serves as the thermal calculation engine for Design Builder, includes a refrigeration module. Moreover, it includes a transcritical refrigeration with CO₂ refrigeration module, ideal for supermarket applications. Comprehensive documentation can be found in the Engineering Reference and input-output guides of EnergyPlus.

This module has received limited attention in academic literature, prompting the authors to cautiously approach its utilization. Rather than relying on it blindly, the authors have opted to replicate the refrigeration system of another supermarket for which enough data is available in existing literature.

A previous work by Mitsopoulos et al. (Mitsopoulos et al., 2019) has been selected as the reference for this validation process. In that paper the CO₂ booster cycle without mechanical subcooling was employed and will be referred as "Reference Cycle" henceforth. In the reference paper empiric data for the refrigeration load, independent from the refrigerant, is also shown and it will be used in sizing the model loads. The EnergyPlus refrigeration model for validation was simulated in Greece, as it is the validation cycle location, with a suitable TMY climate file. The validation required a thermal model so a standard HVACR model with a heat pump and no humidity control, as well as a simplified geometric model was used.

2.1 Refrigeration cycle architecture and operating conditions

Firstly, we present the only architecture of the transcritical CO₂ refrigeration cycle that can be modeled in EnergyPlus. This architecture corresponds to a two-stage CO₂ booster cycle with medium temperature (MT) and low temperature (LT) stages. This cycle comprises the following objects in EnergyPlus (an "object" in Energy Plus refers to any specific named item that can be used to form a model):

- *Refrigeration:TranscriticalSystem*. Models the interactions between cycle objects as well as certain operating parameters.
- *Refrigeration:Case/Refrigeration:WalkIn* and *Refrigeration:CaseAndWalkInList*. Objects that model the different refrigerators, coolers, and walk-in coolers to be reproduced, corresponding to the MT and LT loads of the refrigeration cycle.
- *Refrigeration:Compressor*. One or more compressor objects of the cycle. Models for these can be found in the EnergyPlus database.
- *Refrigeration:GasCooler:AirCooled*. Object that models the gas cooler, the heat exchanger with the exterior of the refrigeration cycle. It will be noted later in this paper that this object has two issues in its operation compared to that of a real one.
- Suction Line Heat Exchanger. This component was not modeled in this work.

The cycle architecture of the system can be observed in **Figure 1**.

average being 1.0, in blue bars for constant load values in one hour intervals. Each vertical line corresponds to 1 hour, starting at 00:00.

Figure 2: Hourly load curve for MT and LT in reference cycle (Mitsopoulos et al., 2019).

The modeling of the restocking effect is relatively straightforward as the LT circuit shows what is expected in a supermarket: The cases are restocked as soon as the supermarket opens for employees, typically at 08:00. This is seen in **Figure 2** as a LT load peak at 08:00. The additional load generated by restocking is a percentage of the standard load for both LT and MT cases.

Openings occur throughout the working hours of the day, as depicted in **Figure 2**, where the load is lower during the night and higher during high activity hours. These three peaks were incorporated into the "Case Credit Fraction Schedule". This schedule is used to add extra load to the refrigeration cases and this extra load is counted as heat removed from the zone as they are caused by openings and thus affect zone temperature. Defrost occurs for 5 minutes each day as per the manufacturer instructions.

2.4 Refrigeration:Compressor

This object does not present issues in its input data since the compressor database available in EnergyPlus is extensive and well-detailed. Subsequent simulations resulted in a correct compressor power consumption. No other specific elements of this object stand out.

2.5 Refrigeration:GasCooler:AirCooled

This object models the gas cooler of the CO₂ Booster cycle. First, some aspects regarding the modeling of the gas cooler fan will be discussed. The gas cooler fan has different types of power curves, which correspond to typical ways of controlling a fan based on its airflow rate. The issue arises precisely in the calculation of the airflow rate, which is based on the ratio between the heat rejected and the gas cooler capacity. The authors have encountered an irregularity in the calculation of the capacity, which is not mentioned in either the literature or the EnergyPlus guide.

The rated capacity is calculated based on a curve described in the EnergyPlus guide as follows: "(Rated) Heat Rejection = C1 + C2 * (gas cooler Outlet Temp - Entering Air Temp, C)". The inconsistency found arises from the programming of the gas cooler capacity. According to the line of code shown in **Figure 3**, obtained from the source code of EnergyPlus, the "RatedCapacity" is calculated for a constant approach temperature of 3 °C. This is the standard value for transcritical systems; however, the approach temperature is never updated via simulation data, which implies that the dependency of the gas cooler capacity with respect to the approach temperature is actually disregarded in the simulations and only considers its value at the mentioned approach=3 °C.

```
GasCooler(GCNum).RatedApproachT = 3.0; // rated CO2 gas cooler approach temperature
if (GasCooler(GCNum).CapCurvePtr > 0) {
    GasCooler(GCNum).RatedCapacity = Curve::CurveValue(state, GasCooler(GCNum).CapCurvePtr, GasCooler(GCNum).RatedApproachT);
}
```

Figure 3: Caption of the Energy Plus source code for gas cooler capacity. (GitHub: <https://github.com/NREL/EnergyPlus/blob/develop/src/EnergyPlus/RefrigeratedCase.cc>)

The second issue is related with the outlet pressure of the CO₂ compressor. The gas cooler sets the compressor outlet pressure using inputs such as the approach in transcritical and subcritical modes, as well as the minimum condensing temperature. The used data are the same as those of the reference

cycle, i.e.: Transcritical Approach = 3 °C, Subcritical Approach = 8 °C and a minimum condensing temperature of 10 °C. This gas cooler model does not allow for simulating pressure losses.

The problem identified in this case lies in the input parameter called "Transition Temperature," which is used by the control of the compressor outlet pressure by the gas cooler. The equations governing this control can be seen in Figure 4. The term " T_{trans} " in the equations represents the transition temperature required as an input by the object.

$$T_{cond} = \begin{cases} T_{cond,min}, & \& T_{amb} \leq T_{cond,min} - \Delta T \\ T_{amb} + \Delta T, & \& T_{cond,min} - \Delta T < T_{amb} \leq T_{trans} - \Delta T \\ T_{trans}, & \& T_{trans} - \Delta T < T_{amb} < T_{trans} \\ T_{sat, P=7.2 MPa}, & \& T_{trans} \leq T_{amb} < 30.978 \end{cases}$$

$$p_{gc} = \begin{cases} 7.5 \times 10^6, & \& T_{amb} < 27 \\ 2.3083 \times 10^5 T_{amb} + 1.190 \times 10^6, & \& T_{amb} \geq 27 \end{cases}$$

Figure 4: Equations for gas cooler pressure operation in Energy Plus

The adopted condensing temperature will be equal to the saturation temperature at P=7.2 MPa if the transition temperature is less than or equal to ambient temperature and less than or equal to 30.978 °C (The latter is the critical temperature of CO₂). At the same time, in transcritical mode, the pressure will remain at 7.5 MPa as long as the outside temperature is below 27 °C. This implies that in the so-called "transition zone," between 22 °C and 27 °C, the pressure is constant in subcritical and then jumps and stays constant until 27 °C in the transcritical mode. It is expected that this outdated control will create a discrepancy between the reference COP and the simulated COP when the outside temperature is between 22 °C and 27 °C.

3 VALIDATION RESULTS

The first result to be discussed is the mentioned irregularity in the gas cooler fan electricity consumption. Through the analysis of the source code, it was inferred that the power consumption for the fan in subcritical mode would be lower than the value provided by the used equations when in subcritical operation.

This result, depicted in **Figure 5**, was not previously discussed in the literature or documentation. In red the EnergyPlus simulated gas cooler fan power consumption; and in black the calculated consumption using simulated data but applying the equations that it should follow if it updated the rated heat transfer capacity as it was discussed in the previous section. As anticipated from examining the source code, the fan consumption in subcritical mode is indeed lower than expected, this is shown as the red curve having lower consumption in subcritical mode ($T_{ext} < 27^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 5: Gas cooler fan consumption calculated (black) and simulated (red)

The subsequent results entail comparisons between the reference cycle from the literature and the simulated cycle. **Figure 6** shows a comparison between the refrigeration loads at medium temperature (MT) and low temperature (LT), regarding outdoors temperature.

The MT load for working days closely follows the reference load, with a discrepancy at low temperatures that is attributed to the absence of humidity control in the simulated HVACR system for this validation. Consequently, during winter, the relative humidity in the supermarket zone is lower, resulting in a reduction of load, especially in the refrigeration cases. As for the non-working days, the discrepancy suggests MT cases in the validation cycle consisted of more closed cases than simulated. These closed cases during non-working days would reduce their load by not being opened. As for LT loads the results show less dependency on internal and external conditions as it was expected, but the results do not follow the reference as closely. Exact case manufacturer data and case distribution would be needed to make further analysis and thus it is left as a limitation of this study.

Figure 6: Load comparison for MT (left) and LT (right)

The dependency on relative humidity for MT load is shown in **Figure 7**. In the upper curve it can be seen that the refrigeration load increases when the lower red curve (relative humidity) increases in winter while the zone temperature stays within the programmed setpoints during different days. With humidity control this relative humidity would be higher and therefore the refrigeration loads for MT at low exterior temperatures would rise.

Figure 7: MT simulated load (W) (Blue, up), zone relative humidity (%) (Red, down) and zone mean air temperature (C) (Green, down).

The next result to be discussed is the COP curve comparison between the reference and the simulated case, shown in **Figure 8**. The simulated COP follows closely the validation cycle COP for most exterior temperatures except in two ranges: At low exterior temperatures (below 10 °C) and within the transition zone (22 °C to 27 °C).

At low temperatures, the MT load being lower than the validation cycle due to not controlling humidity causes the percentage of load corresponding to MT to be lower. Therefore higher percentage of the total load is LT compared to the reference cycle. The average COP is a weighted sum of the COP of MT and

LT compressors weighted to each compressors load. The more LT load there is the lower the average COP. This explains why at low temperatures, where the simulation outputs less MT load than the reference, the simulated COP is lower than the reference COP.

In the transition zone, the simulated COP experiences a drop that was predicted when analyzing the gas cooler pressure control, and it is due to suboptimal gas cooler pressure control in the transition zone. The control should be a linear relationship between Gas Cooler approach and pressure between 22°C and 31°C but is instead simulated as subcritical with constant pressure until T=26°C and transcritical with constant pressure until T=31°C. While this phenomenon is implicitly documented in the documentation, it remains a weakness of the gas cooler model. Regardless of the discussed two effects, the model is capable to reproduce appropriately the COP of the reference refrigeration system. Future work will improve the source code directly to solve this shortcoming.

Figure 8: COP curve comparison

Finally, the main result of this validation process is the comparison of the compressor consumption for each month for the reference and the simulated cases, as depicted in Figure 9. The comparison reveals an absolute mean monthly difference of 5%, accurately reproducing the main consumption of the refrigeration system. The discussed effect of the lower COP in the transition zone is evident, as intermediate months (May, September, October, and November) exhibit higher consumption than the reference cycle. These months correspond to a period where the outside temperature remains mostly within the transition zone.

These results reveal that the transcritical CO₂ refrigeration module of EnergyPlus can be used confidently, as the simulated results closely agree with the reference data. Furthermore, the main sources of discrepancies are now identified and understood.

Figure 9: Compressor consumption each month

4 SUPERMARKET MODELING USING DESIGN BUILDER

Having successfully validated the transcritical refrigeration model in EnergyPlus, the subsequent phase involves its application to our case study: a forthcoming supermarket situated in the IWER building in Pamplona, featuring a subterranean cistern as a TES system. At this preliminary stage of conceptual

engineering, the primary aim of these simulations is to assess the benefits of incorporating the TES system in the particular case of a supermarket. It has been determined that the HVACR system will be heat pump-based, complemented by a photovoltaic system on the roof. However, the specifics regarding changes to the building envelope, the distribution of PV panels on the roof, and the complete definition of the HVACR system will be refined as the project progresses. This paper will present some very preliminary modelling and results of TES simulation in order to show why an appropriate modelling of the refrigeration is necessary for this project.

The project features a BIM model of the entire building generated from a laser point-cloud scan. This BIM model was imported into Design Builder, and the supermarket zone was isolated. The walls connecting to the interior of the IWER building can be simulated as adiabatic, thus saving time by avoiding the simulation of contact areas.

The envelope and enclosures were simulated using the "Medium Weight, moderate insulation" template in Design Builder, with a U-value for the exterior wall of $U=0.351$ ($W/m^2 \cdot K$). The occupancy schedule follows that of commercial premises according to the Spanish Basic Document of Habitability and Energy Efficiency (DBHE), opening from Monday to Saturday with variable occupancy according to the time of day, with employees entering at 07:00 and leaving at 24:00, and closed on Sundays.

The lighting was simulated using LED lights for increased efficiency and equipment consumption was added to simulate ovens, an energy dense process of supermarkets, in this case working in two 3h shifts over the day. Regarding the PV installation on the roof, it spans $541m^2$ of panel surface area with an efficiency of 0.21. While the final project is expected to cover the entire roof along with four other roofs in the IWER building, approximately half of the available PV roof space directly above the supermarket was allocated for the present simulations.

The HVACR control based on temperature setpoint is set to $20^\circ C$ for heating and $25^\circ C$ for cooling (primary control setpoints). Overnight and on Sundays the HVACR is deactivated.

The advanced HVACR system was implemented using heat pumps for heating and cooling. The sizing of the system was carried by following an iterative process, until there were surplus heat pumps that were not in operation during max load hours, resulting in four "ClimateMaster TMW120" heat pumps, with 38kW of heating power and 30kW of cooling power, whose data template is available in Design Builder. The operating temperature for water in the demand circuit is set to $45^\circ C$ for heating and $12^\circ C$ for cooling. Due to a simpler first approach to modeling the HVAC system, individual fan-coil units for the supermarket zone were employed. This limits exterior air control to on or off without fractional values being possible and therefore a nominal $3.8m^3/s$ was determined as satisfying the exterior air regulations for the expected average occupancy of around 0.4 people/ m^2 . This fan-coil does not reproduce for heat recovery, a limitation that will be approached in future detailed HVAC modelling.

Two HVACR systems were modeled: one with and one without TES. The considered volumes for the TES were $420m^3$ and $140m^3$ for hot energy storage and cold energy storage respectively. In total, they account for the available $560m^3$ volume in the cistern. No stratification was modeled as the cistern is wide rather than tall. The setpoint temperature of the TES was always kept with at least $1^\circ C$ from the demand water setpoint in order to ensure heat transfer. The TES is considered charged at $50^\circ C$ for hot and $7^\circ C$ for cold TES respectively. The energy density however cannot be defined for this temperatures as the TES can be overcharged with excess PV as discussed in the next paragraph.

However, properly conducting this feasibility study requires the implementation of a control strategy for the TES. It is known that exploiting energy storage, whether in TES or batteries, depends on utilizing the most beneficial hours to charge the storage and thus avoid consuming energy during the most detrimental hours. In this paper, the following simple control strategy has been applied as a preliminary study: the temperature of the TES is raised (or lowered for Cold TES) when there is a surplus of useful PV energy. A useful surplus is considered as the value that can cover the operation of 2 or more heat pumps. This follows the control mode called "Overcharge" based on the strategy by (Heinz & Rieberer, 2021). The temperatures of the TES can go up to $55^\circ C$ for hot and $2^\circ C$ for cold TES. Thus the temperature deltas are of $4-9^\circ C$ depending of the excess PV production.

The described strategy was implemented in Desing Builder by varying the temperature schedule of the TES. This schedule was constructed through an initial simulation without any control constraints, from which the energy produced by the PV installation, total electrical consumption, and consumption in heat pumps were obtained. Using this data, a "base consumption curve" was built, which resulted in the "curve of excess PV usable for HVACR". This curve was used to schedule maximum PV use. All simulations were conducted for the year 2023. Electricity prices, CO₂ emissions from electricity consumption and PV surplus compensation prices were obtained from the Spanish electric grid operator (REE) web application: "Sistema de Información del Operador del Sistema" (ESIOS). The climatic file used is a TMY dataset for the years 2007-2021 in Pamplona, source: <https://climate.onebuilding.org/>.

5 SIMULATION RESULTS

Two simulation results from our case study are discussed in this section: (i) a comparison of the energy consumption with and without adding refrigeration to the model, which intends to highlight the importance of considering it when simulating a supermarket, and (ii) a comparison between the energy savings for the HVACR systems with and without TES (for a TES control strategy based on a simple PV excess exploitation).

The total electricity consumption without refrigeration is 14.911 MWh/year. Once refrigeration is added, the total increases to 270.839 MWh/year, where refrigeration accounts for 40.7%. This agrees noticeably with results found in the literature (Mylona, Kolokotroni, & Tassou, 2017) and certifies that refrigeration should be taken into account when simulating a supermarket, as it represents a significant consumption factor.

In **Figure 10**, some results of simulating without and with refrigeration in a supermarket are compared. It can be observed that the effect of refrigeration on the HVACR system load is significant. The annual heating consumption increased from 18 MWh to 26.6 MWh when including refrigeration; raising by a factor of 1.42. Meanwhile, the consumption in cooling decreased from 9.4 MWh to 6.2 MWh annually: a third less than the previous value. The same figure shows in the right graph the zone air temperature of the supermarket for a week in January. As the HVAC system is off during the night it can be seen clearly that the zone temperature drops to lower values when taking refrigeration loads into account. This confirms that the influence of refrigerators on HVACR load is significant and its consideration is necessary to attain accurate simulations. This drop in temperature causes a higher heating demand peak during the first hours of the day, and a TES system can be used to supply this peak.

Figure 10: Comparison of supermarket simulation without (Yellow) and with refrigeration (Blue). Heating and cooling demand (left) and Zone Air Temperature (Right)

The second simulation result in our case study refers to the savings in electricity from the grid, electricity costs and CO₂ emissions of that grid electricity. These savings were achieved by utilizing the TES with the PV exploitation control strategy. This strategy achieves the savings shown in **Table 1**. The results demonstrates that, being able to charge during hours of PV production and avoiding HVACR consumption during hours of no PV production, a net electricity saving of 14.74 MWh/year is achieved. In the table the baseline for the savings and percentages was the simulation with no TES.

Electricity from grid savings	(MWh)	14.74	(%)	4.67
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Electricity cost savings	(€)	1893	(%)	3.76
CO ₂ emissions from grid consumption savings	(tonCO ₂)	1.76	(%)	5.21

Table 1: Savings from using PV exploitation control for TES

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study yields two main conclusions: one pertaining to the EnergyPlus transcritical refrigeration capabilities, and the other focusing on the initial results of the TES benefits for its use in a supermarket.

Regarding the EnergyPlus capabilities in modeling transcritical CO₂ refrigeration systems, the validation was deemed positive. It successfully reproduced the refrigeration load's sensitivity to internal and external conditions, COP of the system, and electricity consumption. Some weaknesses were identified in the gas cooler model, particularly in the coding of fan electricity consumption and the suboptimal pressure control for the compressor in the transition zone, leading to a lower modeled COP. Yet, the model can be considered validated, so the supermarket modeling can be adequately carried out by means of a Design Builder-EnergyPlus workflow.

The simulations of the HVACR system for the IWER building in Pamplona, with and without including a TES system (based on an existing water cistern), underscored the significance of accurately modeling refrigeration cases as proper loads. These contribute to nearly half of the electricity consumption and significantly affect the HVACR load, which is crucial for TES simulation and control. The higher heating load, notably high during the first hours of the day as the refrigerators remove heat during the day, and lower cooling load overall necessitate a reconsideration of the size of each TES, while the summer period with high PV production presents an opportunity for new exploitation strategies. The inclusion of a TES system together with a preliminary control strategy, which aimed at maximizing PV consumption, demonstrated energetic and economic savings for the year 2023.

Future work will build upon this study by replicating real supermarket's refrigeration case distributions and further optimizing TES through the implementation of advanced control strategies based on market prices and demand prediction. A more precise and realistic HVAC model will be modeled to take into account humidity control, maximum power constraints, precise exterior airflow calculations, heat recovery and/or economizers, etc. Future approaches should analyze results across different years as to investigate its dependence on market conditions and future trends.

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